

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 63(2) (2025) 224-247

EISSN 2543-5426

Histomorphological and Biochemical Effects of Cancer Polyherbal Formulations and Sorafenib on Experimentally Induced Renal Toxicity in Wistar Rats

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the histomorphological changes associated with the consumption of cancer polyherbal formulations, their interaction with Sorafenib, and their effects on renal toxicity. Sixty Wistar rats (30 males and 30 females) were randomized into ten groups of six rats each. Group A received standard feed and water, Group B received Sorafenib, Groups C and D received polyherbal formulations (Agbo A and Agbo B, respectively), Group E received CCl₄, while Groups F–J received various combinations of CCl₄ with Sorafenib and/or the polyherbal formulations. Biochemical analyses included serum creatinine (Jaffe-slot method), sodium and potassium (ion-selective electrode method), and malondialdehyde (TBARS assay). Histopathological evaluation was performed using Hematoxylin and Eosin staining. Statistical analysis with one-way ANOVA and post hoc testing revealed significant

increases ($p \leq 0.05$) in serum creatinine and potassium levels in the treatment groups compared to controls, whereas sodium and malondialdehyde levels showed no significant changes. Histological examination demonstrated renal tissue alterations such as inflammation, necrosis, hemorrhage, glomerular hypercellularity, and interstitial infiltration. The findings indicate that the polyherbal formulations exert nephrotoxic effects, and their interaction with Sorafenib further aggravates renal injury.

Keywords: Polyherbal formulations, Sorafenib, Renal toxicity, Histomorphology, Nephrotoxicity, Wistar rats, Carbon tetrachloride CCl_4

1. INTRODUCTION

The liver and kidneys are critical xenobiotic metabolic organs responsible for detoxifying, metabolizing, and excreting foreign compounds that are not naturally produced in the body. These foreign compounds, known as xenobiotics, may become toxic and cause structural and functional damage to these organs (Ogenyi et al., 2020). Among these, the kidneys are particularly vulnerable because of their central role in filtration and excretion of waste products, leaving them exposed to toxic metabolites and drug residues.

Polyherbal formulations (PHFs), which combine multiple medicinal plants, are widely consumed in many parts of the world, including Nigeria, for the management of chronic conditions such as cancer. These formulations are believed to provide synergistic therapeutic effects, enhancing efficacy and reducing toxicity compared to single-herb preparations (Madic et al., 2019). They have been reported to possess antioxidant, anti-cancer, anti-diabetic, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties. However, the unregulated consumption of PHFs, often without prescribed dosages or standardized quality control, raises safety concerns. Cases of herb–drug interactions, adulteration, and heavy metal contamination have been documented, leading to adverse renal effects and systemic toxicity (Asif, 2012).

On the other hand, chemotherapy agents such as Sorafenib, a multi-kinase inhibitor targeting the vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) pathway, are widely prescribed for advanced renal cell carcinoma, hepatocellular carcinoma, and thyroid cancer (Jaszai & Schmidt, 2019). Although effective, Sorafenib has been associated with nephrotoxic effects, including hypertension, glomerular injury, and chronic kidney disease (Stavniichuk et al., 2020). Reports are conflicting, however, as some studies suggest Sorafenib may exert protective or mitigating effects under certain experimental conditions (Demirtas et al., 2023), highlighting the need for further investigation.

Carbon tetrachloride (CCl_4) is a well-established experimental model for inducing nephrotoxicity. Its administration leads to oxidative stress and histopathological damage characterized by glomerular degeneration, tubular necrosis, interstitial inflammation, and elevated biochemical markers such as creatinine, sodium, potassium, and malondialdehyde (Elbakry et al., 2015; Ehimigbai & Imariebe, 2022). While some natural extracts, such as *Ocimum gratissimum* leaf, have demonstrated protective effects against CCl_4 -induced nephrotoxicity, the role of PHFs in this context remains poorly understood. Despite the widespread use of polyherbal formulations and conventional chemotherapy in cancer management, limited data exist on their comparative nephrotoxic implications, especially under conditions of xenobiotic-induced renal stress. Understanding these interactions is essential to

inform safer therapeutic practices and prevent renal complications in patients using PHFs alongside chemotherapy drugs. Therefore, the present study was designed to evaluate the histomorphological and biochemical changes in the kidneys of Wistar rats following exposure to selected cancer polyherbal formulations and Sorafenib in the presence of CCl₄-induced renal toxicity. By combining histopathological analysis with renal biomarker assessment, this research provides insight into the nephrotoxic potential of these treatments and their possible interactions, thereby addressing a critical gap in the literature.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study Design

An experimental case–control study was conducted to assess renal histopathological changes induced by polyherbal cancer formulations and Sorafenib in albino rats. Sixty adult Wistar rats (30 males, 30 females) were randomly assigned into ten groups of six (three males and three females each). All procedures complied with the *NIH Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals* and were approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Nnewi Campus. Renal toxicity was induced with 0.3 ml of carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄) dissolved in olive oil (1:1), administered twice weekly for three weeks. Sorafenib (0.3 ml), Agbo A (1 ml), and Agbo B (1 ml) were administered orally via cannula twice weekly, alone or in combination with CCl₄, depending on group assignment. The treatment groups were as follows: Group A (control), Group B (Sorafenib), Group C (Agbo A), Group D (Agbo B), Group E (CCl₄), Group F (CCl₄ + Sorafenib), Group G (CCl₄ + Agbo A), Group H (CCl₄ + Agbo B), Group I (CCl₄ + Sorafenib + Agbo A), and Group J (CCl₄ + Sorafenib + Agbo B). Dosages were determined following established protocols (Lanas et al., 1995) and adjusted according to rat body weight using the formula of Azzam et al. (2014).

2. 2. Study Area

The study was carried out in Okofia, Otolo-Nnewi town in Nnewi-North Local Government Area in Anambra State, South-eastern Nigeria. Nnewi-North LGA has four villages (sub-towns) that make up the one-town local government, which includes: Otolo, Uruagu, Umudim and Nnewi-ichi. Okofia is located at latitude 5° 58' 48" N, and longitude 6° 54' 30" E.

2. 3. Study Duration

The duration for this study spanned for 35 days

2. 4. Ethical Clearance

Ethical approval was sought from the Research Ethical Committee of Faculty of Health Sciences and Technology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Nnewi Campus, before the commencement of this study.

2. 5. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Only healthy adult Albino rats (males and females) which were about 16 weeks of age were included in this study. Pregnant adult female Albino rats were excluded in this study.

2. 6. Procurement of Animals

About 60 healthy adult male and female Albino rats weighing around 100-120g were purchased from an animal farm within Nnewi. The animals were housed in stainless steel community cages at room temperature, relative humidity of about 60-80% and photoperiodicity of 12 h day / 12 h night; and allowed to acclimatize for at least a period of 21 days prior to experiments along with the provision of standard pellet diet and clean water.

2. 7. Animal Sacrifice and Sample Collection

Renal toxicity was induced using CCl₄. After this, the administration of polyherbal cancer formulations and Sorafenib was commenced and the blood samples were collected again and taken to the lab for analysis to determine for changes in Na, K, Creatinine and Malondialdehyde. The experimental animals were weighed, anaesthetised by chloroform at the time of sacrifice, and the kidneys were harvested, weighed, and fixed in a universal container containing 10% neutral buffered formalin for histopathological studies.

2. 8. Histopathological Analysis

Kidney specimens were fixed in 10% buffered formalin and processed using standard paraffin-embedding techniques. Sections of 5 µm thickness were prepared with a rotary microtome and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) to evaluate histomorphological alterations. Hematoxylin stained basophilic structures such as nuclei blue–purple, while eosin counterstained cytoplasmic and extracellular proteins in shades of pink to red (Ochei & Kolhatkar, 2008). Tissue sections were examined under a compound light microscope equipped with photomicrographic facilities by a certified histopathologist. Relative organ weight was calculated as:

$$\text{Relative Organ Weight} = \frac{\text{Total body weight}}{\text{Organ weight}} \times 100$$

2. 9. Biochemical Analyses

2. 9. 1. Electrolytes (Na⁺ and K⁺)

Serum sodium and potassium concentrations were determined using an ion-selective electrode (ISE) analyzer (Biobase). The principle is based on potentiometry, where the potential difference across a selective membrane is measured (Raghbir, 2019). Reference ranges: Na⁺ = 135–155 mmol/L; K⁺ = 3.5–5.5 mmol/L.

2. 9. 2. Creatinine

Serum creatinine was measured by the Jaffe alkaline picrate method, in which creatinine reacts with picrate in an alkaline solution to form an orange–red complex, measured spectrophotometrically at 490 nm (Ochei & Kolhatkar, 2008). Reference values: males = 35–50 µmol/L (0.5–0.8 mg/dl), females = 25–40 µmol/L (0.2–0.5 mg/dl)

2. 9. 3. Malondialdehyde (MDA)

Lipid peroxidation was estimated as malondialdehyde (MDA) using the thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) method. Serum was reacted with trichloroacetic acid and

thiobarbituric acid, heated at 95–100 °C for 30 minutes, extracted with n-butanol, and centrifuged. The absorbance of the supernatant was measured at 530 nm, and results were expressed in µmol/L using an extinction coefficient of 1.56×10^5 L/mol/cm (Aguilar & Borges, 2020).

2. 10. Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis was carried out using Graphpad Prism Software (version 10.1). The experimental data was expressed as the mean ± standard error of mean. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Post hoc test were used to analyse the data. The limit for statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

Table 1. Changes in body weight of experimental animals before and following exposure herbal medicine and chemotherapy (Mean ± SEM).

Group	Initial weight (g)	Final weight (g)	t-value	P-value
A	131.75±3.50	150.00±7.45	-2.729	0.072
B	182.00±9.63	158.75±8.44	5.958	0.009**
C	182.00±9.95	167.50±12.58	2.945	0.060
D	165.25±18.83	174.25±10.57	-0.481	0.664
E	195.25±6.95	215.50±7.44	-3.213	0.049*
F	171.75±21.25	161.75±22.49	0.234	0.830
G	178.25±16.65	164.00±17.48	0.566	0.611
H	182.25±8.37	168.50±9.33	1.696	0.188
I	171.75±10.77	148.50±6.12	2.358	0.100
J	167.00±13.83	158.25±9.58	1.072	0.362

Paired samples t-test, * Significant mean difference at $P < 0.05$.

Group: A - Negative control, B - Sorafenib, C - Agbo A, D - Agbo B, E - CCL-4 (Positive control), F - Sorafenib, G - CCL-4 and Agbo A, H - CCL-4 and Agbo B, I -CCL-4, Sorafenib and Agbo A, J - CCL-4, Sorafenib and Agbo B.

There was a significant decrease in the body weight of wistar rats that were administered sorafenib only (group B) when compared with that of the negative control (A) ($P < 0.05$).

There was a significant increase in the body weight of the wistar rats that were administered CCL-4 only (group E) ($P < 0.05$).

Table 2. Changes in body weight of experimental animals before and following exposure herbal medicine and chemotherapy (expressed in mean ± SEM).

Group	Relative Kidney Weight	F-value	P-value
A	0.0077±0.0006	1.149	
B	0.0061±0.0049		0.011*
C	0.0067±0.0005		0.102
D	0.0073±0.0002		0.503
E	0.0070±0.0004		0.212
F	0.0074±0.0004		0.574
G	0.0074±0.0007		0.562
H	0.0068±0.0001		0.134
I	0.0072±0.0002		0.383
J	0.0071±0.0002		0.336

One-way ANOVA, Post Hoc LSD, *Significant mean difference at P<0.05.

Group: A - Negative control, B - Sorafenib, C - Agbo A, D - Agbo B, E - CCL-4 (Positive control), F - Sorafenib, G - CCL-4 and Agbo A, H - CCL-4 and Agbo B, I - CCL-4, Sorafenib and Agbo A, J - CCL-4, Sorafenib and Agbo B.

There was a significant decrease in the relative kidney weight of wistar rats that were administered sorafenib (group B) when compared to that of the negative control (group A) (P<0.05).

Table 3. Results of the heavy metals analysis in the two selected herbal formulations under research.

Parameters	Sample A	Sample B	Who Standard in Water (mg/l)
Magnesium (ppm)	0.580	0.715	30
Sodium (ppm)	2.287	4.505	200
Calcium (ppm)	2.034	2.045	200
Iron (ppm)	0.054	0.348	0.30
Manganese (ppm)	0.042	0.042	0.02
Mercury (ppm)	0.236	0.100	0.006

Lead (ppm)	1.029	0.853	0.01
Chromium (ppm)	0.00	0.00	0.05
Arsenic (ppm)	0.006	0.042	0.01
Cadmium (ppm)	0.772	0.405	0.003
Zinc (ppm)	3.012	1.919	3.00
Phosphorus (ppm)	5.554	5.834	1.00

Table 3 shows that Iron and Arsenic are slightly elevated in sample B, Zinc is slightly elevated in Sample A and Manganese, Mercury, Lead, Cadmium and phosphorus are elevated in both herbal drug as stated by (World Health Organization, 2017) permissible limit of heavy metals in drinking water.

3. 1. Photomicrograph showing effects of carbon tetrachloride, cancer polyherbal formulations and sorafenib on the kidney histomorphology of animals in various groups

Figure 1. Group A (Control): A H & E stained kidney section showing normal renal architecture. X10 objective.

Figure 2. Group B (Chemotherapy): A H & E stained kidney tissue showing enlarged glomerulus with increased cellularity and mesangial expansion and interstitial congestion (arrow). X10 objective.

Figure 3. Group C (Agbo A): A H&E stained kidney tissue showing haemorrhage (Arrow). X10 objective.

Figure 4. Group D (Agbo B): A H &E stained kidney tissue showing inflammation (Arrow). X10 objective.

Figure 5. Group E (CCl₄): A H &E stained kidney tissue showing severe inflammation (Arrow). X10 objective.

Figure 6. Group F (CCl₄ + Sorafenib): A H &E stained kidney tissue suggestive of glomerulonephritis due to an enlarged glomerulus with increased cellularity and mesangial expansion (Arrow). X10 objective.

Figure 7. Group G (CCl₄ + Agbo A): A H&E stained kidney tissue showing an interstitial infiltration (Arrow). X10Objective.

Figure 8. Group H (CCl₄ + Agbo B): A H &e stained kidney tissue showing inflammation (arrow). X4 objective.

Figure 9. Group I (CCl₄ + Sorafenib + Agbo A): A H &E stained kidney tissue showing an increased glomeruli cellularity(arrow). x10 objective.

Figure 10. Group J (CCl_4 + Sorafenib + Agbo B): A H &E stained kidney tissue showing an interstitial infiltration (arrow). X10 objective.

The bar chart above shows the differences between the mean potassium of group A, B, C and D. There is a significant difference between the mean(s) of the potassium levels of each group. There was a significant difference (increase) in the mean potassium levels when Group A (control) was compared with Group B (chemotherapy). The error bar indicates the standard error of mean for each group.

Figure 11. Mean Comparisons of potassium levels of Groups A, B, C and D (Mean \pm Standard Error of Mean; SEM). Statistical analysis: ANOVA and Post hoc test. Significance is set at $p \leq 0.05$.

The figure above shows the differences in the mean potassium levels across the various experiment groups. There was a significant difference between the mean potassium levels of the experiment groups. There was a significant difference (increase) between mean potassium levels of group A (control) and group B (chemotherapy). There was a significant difference (increase) in mean potassium levels when group A (control) was compared with group E (CCl₄). There was a significant difference (decrease) between the mean potassium levels of group B (chemotherapy) and group J (CCl₄ + Chemotherapy + Agbo A). There was also a significant difference (decrease) between the mean potassium levels of group E (CCl₄) and group G (CCl₄ + Agbo A). Similarly, there was a significant difference (decrease) in the mean potassium levels of group E (CCl₄) when compared with group H (CCl₄ + Agbo B). A significant difference (decrease) was also observed between the mean potassium levels of group E (CCl₄) and group I (CCl₄ + chemotherapy + Agbo A). The results further showed a significant difference (decrease) in the mean potassium levels of group E (CCl₄) when compared with group J (CCl₄ + chemotherapy + Agbo B).

Figure 12. Mean Comparison of Potassium Levels across the Experiment Groups (Mean \pm SEM). Statistical analysis: ANOVA and Post hoc test. Significance is set at $p \leq 0.05$.

The bar chart above shows the differences in the mean creatinine levels in Groups A, B, C and D. There was a significant difference between the mean creatinine levels of the groups. There was a significant difference (increase) in the mean creatinine levels when group A (control) was compared with group B (chemotherapy). There was a significant difference (increase) between the mean creatinine levels of group A (control) and group C (Agbo A).

There was also a significant difference (decrease) between group B (chemotherapy) and group D (Agbo B) mean creatinine levels.

Figure 13. Mean Comparison between the Creatinine levels of Groups A, B, C and D (Mean \pm SEM). Statistical analysis: ANOVA and *Post hoc* test. Significance is set at $p \leq 0.05$.

The bar chart shows the differences in the mean of the creatinine levels across the experimental groups. There was a significant difference between the mean creatinine levels of the experimental groups. There was a significant difference (increase) between the mean creatinine levels of group A (control) and group B (chemotherapy).

Figure 14. Mean Comparison of Creatinine Levels across Experimental Groups (Mean \pm SEM). Statistical analysis: ANOVA and *Post hoc* test. Significance is set at $p \leq 0.05$.

There was also a significant difference (increase) between the mean creatinine levels of group A (control) and group C (Agbo A). Similarly, a significant difference (increase) was seen between group A (control) and group G (CCl₄ + Agbo A) mean creatinine levels. There was a significant difference (increase) in the mean creatinine levels when group A (control) was compared with group H (CCl₄ + Agbo B). There was no significant difference between the mean sodium levels of groups A, B, C and D.

Figure 15. Mean Comparison of Sodium Levels in Groups A, B, C and D (Mean ± SEM). Statistical analysis: ANOVA and *Post hoc* test. Significance is set at $p \leq 0.05$.

There was no significant difference between the mean sodium levels of the experimental groups

Figure 16. Mean comparison of sodium levels across experimental Groups (Mean ± SEM). Statistical analysis: ANOVA and *Post hoc* test. Significance is set at $p \leq 0.05$.

There was no significant difference between the mean malondialdehyde levels of the experimental groups

Figure 17. Mean comparisons of Malondialdehyde levels in Groups A,B,C, and D (Mean \pm SEM). Statistical analysis: ANOVA and *Post hoc* test. Significance is set at $p \leq 0.05$.

There was no significant difference between the mean malondialdehyde levels of the experimental groups

Figure 18. Mean comparisons of Malondialdehyde levels across experimental Groups (Mean \pm SEM). Statistical analysis: ANOVA and *Post hoc* test. Significance is set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Table 4. Relationship between malondialdehyde and some renal function parameters.

	Creatinine		Sodium		Potassium		Malondialdehyde	
	r- value	p-value	r-value	p-value	r-value	p-value	r-value	p-value
Creatinine			0.213	0.317	0.544	0.006*	-0.250	0.238
Sodium	0.213	0.317			0.234	0.271	-0.195	0.362
Potassium	0.544	0.006*	0.234	0.271			-0.203	0.342
Malondialdehyde	-0.250	0.238	-0.195	0.362	-0.203	0.342		

The result showed a strong positive relationship between potassium and creatinine ($p = 0.006$).

4. DISCUSSION

The kidney is central to metabolic homeostasis and detoxification, but its role in xenobiotic metabolism makes it highly vulnerable to toxic injury. In this study, renal damage was induced by carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄), and the effects of Sorafenib and polyherbal formulations (Agbo A and Agbo B) were examined in Wistar rats.

Table 1 showed that there was a significant decrease in body weight in the group treated with Sorafenib and a significant increase in body weight in the group treated with CCl₄. The loss of weight associated with Sorafenib is one of its toxic properties. In a study carried out on Sorafenib, escalation from 30 to 60 mg/kg sorafenib improved antitumor efficacy but worsened survival due to excessive body weight loss (Kuczynski *et al.*, 2015). However, escalating the dose may be an effective treatment strategy, provided the toxicity can be controlled. Another study showed the effect of sorafenib on low skeletal muscle mass (LSMM) patients (Sawada *et al.*, 2019). These patients tend to come down with more toxic effects of Sorafenib compared to non-LSMM patients.

The increase in body weight in the group treated with CCl₄ in table 1 reveals that the CCl₄ group may have recovered from toxic effects since only a single intraperitoneal administration of CCl₄ was given. Usually, CCl₄ administration induces weight loss and loss of appetite especially when it is continually administered (Okamoto *et al.*, 2001). Although weight loss is not a direct or common symptom of carbon tetrachloride exposure. Weight loss is a consequence of severe health deterioration rather than a direct effect of the chemical (Okamoto *et al.*, 2001). Weight loss is not an immediate symptom of a single exposure, but it could occur if the kidney damage impairs metabolic functions and appetite over time.

Table 2 showed that there was a significant decrease in kidney weight in the group treated with Sorafenib only compared to group A which is the negative control group. Sorafenib has been associated with renal toxicity which can potentially lead to changes in kidney weight. These alterations in renal function and structure, can lead to either swelling (increasing kidney weight) or atrophy (decreasing kidney weight) depending on the severity and duration of

exposure (Singh, *et al.*, 2022). The photomicrographs in the 3.2. section from Figure 1 - 12 show the effects of these substances on the histomorphology of the kidney. Group A as the control shows a normal glomerulus. Group B, the chemotherapy-treated group showed an enlarged glomerulus with hypercellularity, mesangial expansion and interstitial congestion. The Agbo A- treated group, group C showed a possible hyaline glomerulopathy and the Agbo-B treated group showed inflammation. For group E, the administration of CCl₄ showed inflammation. Group F (CCl₄ and Sorafenib) showed an enlarged glomerulus, with increased mesangial cellularity and mesangial expansion, suggestive of glomerulonephritis. Group G (CCl₄ and Agbo A) revealed an interstitial infiltration. Group H (CCl₄ and Agbo B) showed inflammation at the renal pelvis. Group I (CCl₄ + Sorafenib + Agbo A) showed increased glomerular cellularity and Group J (CCl₄ + Sorafenib + Agbo B) showed interstitial infiltration.

The sections reveal that all the substances that were administered compromised the kidneys' architecture compared to the control group which showed normal kidney structure. The groups treated with Sorafenib showed extreme damage while groups involving PHFs showed minimal damage (Aswar *et al.*, 2022).

Tables 1 and 2 showed the phytochemical constituents of these selected polyherbal formulations. One of these chemical constituents is oxycodone (Table 1) which is an analgesic for cancer pain (Ordóñez *et al.*, 2017). This is useful as it can take care of the pains that ensue as a result of cancer. In contrast, a prolonged exposure to another constituent, 2,4,7-Trinitrofluorenone (Table 1) can lead to eye and skin irritation. When heated to decomposition, it emits highly toxic fumes of nitrogen oxides (National Center for Biotechnology Information, 2024).

However, the other beneficial properties of these polyherbal formulations like anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antitumor, antimicrobial, are relevant to this study. Some of these constituents exert toxic effects on the kidney. Streptonigrin generates ROS and induces oxidative stress, leading to kidney damage (Nasir *et al.*, 2023). Chrysene is a polycyclic aromatic compound known for its potential carcinogenic and nephrotoxic properties. It can cause renal damage through oxidative stress and DNA damage mechanisms (Meng *et al.*, 2016). Although lormetazepam is primarily known for its CNS effects, prolonged use or overdose of benzodiazepines can lead to impaired renal function due to metabolic disturbances (Liao *et al.*, 2021).

In addition, the quantity of each heavy metal present in these polyherbals were evaluated in Table 4. These heavy metals do not have a prompt impact on the body. The human body cannot discharge these metals and they keep accumulating in the body. Overtime, they begin to manifest certain deleterious effects in the liver, lungs, kidneys and other vital organs. They also pose a risk of cancer as some of these heavy metals are carcinogenic. Mercury, lead and cadmium in drinking water can cause damage to the kidneys. Arsenic can cause skin and eye irritation (Rehman *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, this implies that prolonged consumption of these polyherbals may cause kidney damage. This is due to the alarming quantities of these heavy metals in these polyherbals.

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This was also confirmed by another study of the effect of sorafenib on low skeletal muscle mass (LSMM) patients (Sawada *et al.*, 2019). These patients tend to come down with more toxic effects of Sorafenib compared to non-LSMM patients.

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The statistical analysis showed the differences in the mean levels of potassium, creatinine, sodium and malondialdehyde. These were the parameters that were analysed after the administration of the different substances assigned to each group. The differences in the mean potassium levels across the experiment indicate the effects of sorafenib, CCl₄ and polyherbal formulations on the parameter. The mean potassium level was significantly elevated in the sorafenib-treated group when compared to the control group. This shows that sorafenib induced hyperkalemia (Ummugul *et al.*, 2012). Compared to the control group, the mean potassium level was also elevated in the group treated with carbon tetrachloride (Asejeje *et al.*, 2020). While mild hyperkalemia may be asymptomatic, high potassium levels may cause life-threatening cardiac arrhythmias, muscle weakness or paralysis (Simon *et al.*, 2023). High potassium level is also an important pointer to impaired kidney function or disease. Consequently, limb paralysis in some wistar rats was one of the physical observations of administering CCl₄ and sorafenib. Compared to the mean potassium levels in sorafenib and CCl₄ treated groups, the mean potassium levels in the control groups and polyherbal groups were significantly decreased ($p \leq 0.05$). This implies that the polyherbal formulations may have some ameliorative effect to combat the increased potassium levels associated with CCl₄ and sorafenib (Asejeje *et al.*, 2020).

The mean creatinine levels were significantly elevated in groups treated with sorafenib and polyherbal formulations ($p \leq 0.05$) compared to the control group, CCl₄-treated group and Agbo-B treated group D. This implies that sorafenib and polyherbal formulation A compromised the kidney functions of the wistar rats. The CCl₄-treated group did not show elevated creatinine levels probably because only a single-peritoneal administration was carried out. Exposure of these rats to CCl₄ was discontinued after inducing renal toxicity once. It is possible that the body system of the rats had initiated a healing mechanism to reverse the creatinine levels to near normal levels. This is because the mean creatinine levels of the CCl₄-treated group were slightly elevated than the mean creatinine levels of the control group though not significant. The Agbo B - treated group showed a slightly elevated mean creatinine level compared to the control group A. This implies that compared to the Agbo A polyherbal formulations, Agbo B polyherbal formulation compromised the kidney function lesser than

Agbo A polyherbal formulation. Elevated creatinine levels indicate impaired or compromised kidney function which may be temporary or sustained in cases of chronic renal diseases.

The mean sodium levels across the experimental groups did not show any significant difference. CCl₄ is known to impair kidney functions by increasing the sodium levels (Asejeje *et al.*, 2020). In contrast, this study showed that there was no significant difference in the mean sodium levels of CCl₄-treated group and control group. This could be as a result of carrying out a single peritoneal administration of CCl₄ which was not strong enough to elevate sodium levels or other factors which also affected the mean sodium levels of other groups. Even after mean creatinine levels were elevated, there are reasons why the differences between the mean sodium levels of the experimental groups are not significant. Selective renal damage where substances like Sorafenib and the polyherbals may cause selective damage to the renal tubules or glomeruli, leading to increased creatinine levels due to impaired filtration, while not significantly affecting sodium reabsorption or excretion. The body has robust compensatory mechanisms to maintain sodium homeostasis, including hormonal regulation (e.g., aldosterone, antidiuretic hormone), which might compensate for any disruptions caused by the. These compensatory mechanisms can help stabilise serum sodium levels.

If the exposure to the toxic substance is acute, the effects on sodium balance might not manifest immediately, while creatinine levels, which reflect glomerular filtration rate (GFR), might show changes more rapidly. Chronic exposure might eventually lead to altered sodium levels if compensatory mechanisms fail. The Wistar rats were only exposed for two weeks (two days per week) to Sorafenib and polyherbal formulations. This does not reflect a chronic exposure enough to alter mean sodium levels of the experimental groups. Sorafenib and the polyherbal formulations may not have directly interfered with sodium balance but instead affected other aspects of renal function that influence creatinine levels. For example, some nephrotoxic agents that may be in Sorafenib and polyherbal formulations might induce glomerular damage without affecting tubular sodium handling significantly.

The timing of the measurement after administering the substance can also be crucial. Sodium levels might fluctuate transiently but return to baseline due to homeostatic adjustments by the time of measurement, whereas creatinine levels, which reflect kidney filtration function, might remain altered. This was observed in CCl₄-treated groups. The measurement time of the sodium levels was after two weeks of inducing renal toxicity with CCl₄. Therefore, the increase in sodium levels following renal toxicity could not be captured (Wallis, 2024).

The mean malondialdehyde (MDA) levels of the experimental groups did not show any significant difference. MDA is an oxidative stress marker and it is used in clinical and research settings to assess oxidative stress in diseases. Elevated MDA levels are associated with increased oxidative damage. It is an indicator of lipid peroxidation. The mean MDA level of the control group was higher than that of other groups that were treated with toxic substances; though not significant. This is an unexpected outcome, hence some explanation for this occurrence.

The Wistar rats exposed to CCl₄, Sorafenib and polyherbal formulations might have activated adaptive responses that upregulate their antioxidant defences, leading to a more efficient neutralisation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and consequently lower MDA levels (Sies, 2017).

Also, the exposure to CCl₄, Sorafenib and polyherbal formulations could induce the expression of detoxifying enzymes like glutathione peroxidase, superoxide dismutase, and catalase, which mitigate oxidative stress and reduce MDA formation (Vallko *et al.*, 2006).

The doses of Sorafenib, CCl₄ and polyherbal formulations were administered in a dose that is sublethal or insufficient to cause extensive lipid peroxidation, the body might cope effectively with the induced stress, resulting in lower MDA levels. (Calabrese, 2018). Chronic low-level exposure of the Wistar rats to the substance can cause the induction of protective mechanisms over time while acute exposure could overwhelm the system potentially causing diverse effects on MDA levels. The administration of Sorafenib and the polyherbals was not acute, the half-life of Sorafenib was used to determine the intervals between dosage. This explains why the MDA levels were not affected (Halliwell and Gutteridge 2015).

Environmental factors such as diet, housing conditions, and stress could influence oxidative stress levels in both the control and treated groups. There may also be inherent biological variability among the wistar rats, and the control group might have had higher baseline levels of MDA due to random fluctuations or differences in metabolism (Kohen and Nyska, 2002).

The methods used to measure MDA may have introduced variability. For example, the TBARS assay can sometimes produce variable results due to the presence of interfering substances. The timing of sample collection may have affected the MDA levels. If samples were collected at a time when antioxidant responses were at their peak in the treated group, lower MDA levels might be observed (Pompella *et al.*, 2003)

Low doses of polyherbal formulation might induce a hormetic response, where the exposure leads to adaptive beneficial effects, enhancing the organism's stress resistance and reducing MDA levels (Mattson, 2008).

These substances might act through mechanisms that do not directly elevate lipid peroxidation or might involve pathways that decrease MDA levels as a secondary effect (Klaassen and Watkins, 2015).

Further on statistical analysis, the correlation Table 4 shows a strong positive relationship between potassium and creatinine. This can be explained by certain reasons. A decrease in glomerular filtration rate (GFR) can lead to decreased excretion of both potassium and creatinine, causing their levels to rise in the blood. In addition, conditions that cause hyperkalemia often concur with conditions that affect kidney function, leading to elevated creatinine. Some of these conditions include acute kidney injury, severe dehydration, chronic kidney disease, hormonal and endocrine disorders and metabolic acidosis (Wallis, 2024).

5. CONCLUSION

Polyherbal formulations used in this study have shown some toxic effects which were seen in the results. The creatinine levels were elevated in groups treated with sorafenib and polyherbal formulations. This is to say in fact that the kidney functions were compromised due to administration of these polyherbal formulations.

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